

Enhancing Competitiveness of the Indonesian Film Industry: A Value Chain Approach

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The Indonesian film industry has undergone substantial transformation due to technological advancements and shifts in consumer behavior. Porter's (1985) original value chain concept has been widely adapted to represent the film industry's activities, encompassing content creation, distribution, and exhibition. This study employs a comprehensive literature review to chronologically uncover the value chain's evolution in the film sector as a theoretical framework for the film industry and to answer how the value chain framework enhances the competitiveness of the film industry. The methodology involves a structured search strategy across diverse sources, supplemented by snowballing, aiming to extract insights into integrating the value chain model within the industry. The findings demonstrate that the value chain concept signifies interconnections among different stages of the film industry, enhancing value creation and competitive advantage, with impacts on digitization and digital distribution. This comprehension enhances the industry's ability to create value, gain a competitive edge, and navigate digitization and digital distribution challenges and opportunities. By recognizing the interdependencies within the value chain, the Indonesian film industry can strategically optimize its processes, adapt to evolving trends, and make informed decisions that increase competitiveness. In bridging theoretical foundations with practical implications, the study's findings contribute to an enriched understanding of the Indonesian film industry's dynamics, value creation, and competitive strategies while providing valuable insights for practitioners, researchers, and stakeholders.

Keywords: value chain, Indonesian film industry, competitiveness, digital distribution model

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Andi Surja Boediman, a CEO at Ideosource Entertainment and Managing Partner at Ideosource Venture Capital, is currently pursuing a Doctorate in Technology Management at Institut Teknologi Sepuluh Nopember. He's invested in over 15 films, including "Losmen Bu Broto," "Gundala," and "Keluarga Cemara," and has backed 30+ tech startups, like Bibit/Stockbit and eFishery.

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Dr Baihaqi earned his PhD from Monash University Australia. While he was pursuing his doctorate degree, he also works as tutor, teaching assistance and research assistant in Department of Management, Australia. He also taught in School of Business, Monash University Sunway Campus for almost two years (2009-2011). Prior to joining a lecturer, he worked as programmer and system analyst. His main research interests are management and information technology, specifically in relation operations and supply chain management. He particularly interested in field research employing survey and case study methodology.